

**WHO IS MORE DANGEROUS? OBESITY OR MEDICAL DISCOURSE ON
OBESITY: A CDA OF DISCOURSE OF RESEARCH ARTICLES AND MEDICAL
ASSOCIATIONS**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8163368>

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Received June: 23/2023.

Accepted July: 15/2023.

Published July: 18/2023.

Abstract

The study looked at the medical discourse surrounding obesity to investigate how research journal articles and obesity disease associations express suggestions for patients' diets. The study looked at how associations' recommendations modify speech in order to delete information, as well as how selection, generalization, and construction are used to manipulate discourse. For the critical discourse analysis of suggestions by research articles and associations, the researcher used Van Dijk's macrostructure model of discourse. For the analysis of data acquired from articles and other web publications, AntConc and Excel were employed. The study included a total of ten research publications and eight associations' recommendations. The study's findings revealed that associations engage in such behaviors due to a variety of constraints that prevent them from providing a complete discourse. In this way the discourse related to obesity disease is manipulated and health of patients is put on risk.

Keywords: Obesity, Discourse, Research, Journals, Associations

Introduction

Obesity is a complex condition characterized by an excess of body fat. It's a medical condition that raises the chance of various diseases and health issues like high blood

pressure, type 2 diabetes, coronary heart disease, cancer, and obstructive sleep apnea, to name a few. Body fat is most often and easily calculated in clinical practice using a formula that combines weight and height. The fundamental assumption is that fat mass accounts for the majority of weight difference among people of the same height, and the formula most commonly employed in epidemiological studies is body mass index (BMI).

The Build and Blood Pressure Study found that the negative effects of excess weight can take ten years or more to manifest. Increased levels of overweight and obesity are strong predictors of shorter longevity, according to life insurance statistics and epidemiological studies. The chance of dying within 26 years increased by 1% for each additional pound (0.45 kg) gained in weight between the ages of 30 and 42, and by 2% between the ages of 50 and 62, according to the Framingham Heart Study. BMI the square of the height in meters divided by the weight in kilos circumference of the waist measured at the halfway between the lower border of the ribs and the top border of the pelvis (in cm). Thickness of the skinfold When skinfold thickness (in centimeters) is measured with calipers at various locations, a more precise assessment can be made. Bioimpedance Lean mass carries electricity better than fat mass, according to this theory.

Types of Obesity

Food obesity (excessive intake of sugar, saturated fats)

Thickness of nervous stomach (caused by anxiety, depression and stress)

Gluten diet (usually present in women due to hormonal imbalance, menopause)

Genetic metabolic obesity (People whose stomach often swollen like a balloon, accumulates fats in the middle of the body)

Thickness due to Venous Circulation (genetic inherited obesity, often in people who have swollen legs). Thickness of inactivity (this affects parts of the body which in the past have been very active in people who play sports)

Obesity is a complex disease that is caused in part by a long-term positive energy balance, which occurs when energy expenditure exceeds nutritional energy intake. Excess energy is converted to triglycerides, which are deposited in adipose tissue, resulting in a rise in body fat and, as a result, weight gain. Passive overconsumption of energy-dense, nutrient-poor, processed, and inexpensive foods and beverages, as well as a decrease in physical activity, have been identified as important contributors to the obesity epidemic. (Obesity as a medical problem, Peter G. Kopelman.

Purpose Statement

It's all about understanding language in context, including background knowledge and the goals that drive the language, as well as the actions that occur as a result of specific lexical choices. Discourse, on the other hand, is the study of text production, discursive practice, and social practice. Discourse is about who is speaking to whom, what, why, how, and where. This work is a qualitative and descriptive study of medical text analysis; I have examined the similarities and variations in medical research and association directories recommendations in this paper. Researchers are more explicit and exact on a textual level, speaking or using language simply at the level of information delivery, ignoring social context, class, or set up completely. While associations put forward a list of possible treatments adopted during the obesity and do not present the recommendations in the form of the different levels of obesity. Disease causes are primarily focused, but what should be the next step, what should people who are suffering from this type of disease do to live a healthy life?

Research Objectives

The study has following objectives

- To find out the difference and similarities between Associations and Journals about Obesity?
- To comprehend the major differences between medical association's discourse and research journal suggestions
- To interpret hidden realities using Van Dijk's discourse model
- To learn how effective obesity treatment was obliterated by medical guidelines.
- To expose a medical association's selection factor
- To Define the function of generalization in medical associations.
- To elaborate, how might linguistic varieties help associations form schema through events?

Research Questions

The study has following questions

- What is the discourse in distinctions and similarities on obesity related associations and journals?
- How concealed realities be revealed on the basis of discourse?

- How to understand the difference between the discourse of medical associations and research journals recommendations?
- How did medical recommendations delete effective obesity treatment?
- How do medical associations use the revealed element of selection?
- What methods do we use to find generalization in research journals and medical organizations?
- How schematic events of associations can be assisted through linguistic variants?

Literature Review

Discourse and Language

DA is a discipline that is old as well as new. Discourse analysis has progressed from linguistic to socialistic approaches throughout its history. Its roots can be traced back over 2000 years to the study of language, public discourse, and literature. Classical rhetoric, or the art of good speaking, is clearly an important source of information. The sister discipline of rhetorical dealt with the precepts for the planning, organization, specific operations, and performance of public speech in political and legal settings, whereas grammatical, the historical antecedent of linguistics, was concerned with the normative rules of correct language use

Michel Foucault's work is important when considering how power is exercised over the (female, reproductive) body in Western civilization (Rail & Harvey, 1995, p. 165). Power, according to Foucault, is a result of speech that operates inside daily exchanges between people and institutions, rather than something controlled by specific persons or organizations and utilized to oppress others (Burr, 2003, p. 68). As a result, power is inextricably linked to knowledge creation and the ability to define what is considered truth or reality in society. The body is formed by and exists in speech, becoming a fundamental location of power relations when viewed through a Foucauldian lens. "The body for Foucault is not simply a subject of discourse," Shilling (2003) explains, "but constitutes the link between daily behaviours on the one hand and large-scale power organization on the other". Another noteworthy example of the contribution that discourse-based techniques can make is Skillington (1998). In his research, he examines the renovation of Dublin's city centre using a textual focused analysis based on Fairclough. Skillington claims that symbolic and referential discourses have developed an insular dominant paradigm that favors a strict division of public and private space, making progressive or alternative views of urban revitalization impossible to build. He analyses how structural power relationships are maintained through narratives about urban redevelopment using evidence from stories published in the Irish Times newspaper in the early 1990s.

Females are more likely to exercise the appropriate medical monitoring. Prescriptions for proper exercise were given to women in all stages of life, including infancy and preadolescence, reproductive age (15 to 45), and middle or old age (women beyond 45). (Vertinsky, 1988). The onset of puberty, in particular, was a crucial event since it

signaled a moment when females had to start conserving energy in order to maintain optimal reproduction development. Girlhood's unfettered play had to come to an end, and more acceptable pursuits in the kitchen, the lavatory, and the garden ("nature's gymnasia for adolescent girls") had to take its place (Vertinsky, 1988). According to Van Dijk (2000), ideology plays a critical role in the positive representation of some groups and the bad image of others. Politicians and the media frequently use the SELF and OTHERS debate. In other words, in-group individuals are always shown positively, and out-group members are always portrayed negatively. Given the overwhelming evidence that current meat consumption levels endanger human and environmental health, Government intervention is required to minimize meat intake (i.e., Meat Curtailment Policies, or MCPs). However, few of these policies are actually enforced, owing to concerns about blowback. Improved comprehension.

DISCOURSE AND IDEOLOGY

As a result, recognizing the ideological underpinnings of backlash is critical for developing methods that can help advance the long-awaited progress. Make the switch to a diet that is more plant-based. To solve this situation, the research examines the various conceptual perspectives. Backlash against MCPs is shaped by certain ideas. Three articles in right-wing publications, as well as almost 2700 comments, in reaction to a Facebook post legislative measures in the Netherlands to reduce animal protein consumption. The data is analyzed using a methodology for analyzing ideological rhetoric, which allows ideological conceptions to be identified by recognizing semantic and formal structures in text.

In addition to the well-known neoliberal (e.g., freedom of choice) and carnal concepts (Meat, for example, is normal), the research demonstrates that populist ideas are dangerous. a substantial conceptual underpinning of reaction. Furthermore, ideologies associated with Anti-elitism communism are linked to communism and carnism. The study aids in a greater comprehension of the sociopolitical the nature of anti-MCP sentiment. It implies that, while ideas about carnism can help people excuse their meat consumption, they are only partially significant in amplification MCP confrontation. This kind of resistance isn't just an individual reaction; it's a topic around which people unite around common ideas. (Yolie J.E. Michielsen & Horst, 2022).

In this article, a discourse analysis is used to identify discourses in scientific writings on diagnostic radiography. From February 2009 through August 2013, the material comprised of 45 papers from the journal Radiography. There were four main discourses discovered. Technology-centered, patient-centered, uncertain patient, and invisible patient discourses were called after them. Patients were frequently perceived as an anonymous group in the technology-centered discourse, and they were passive. Patients' experiences were frequently sought in the patient-centered discourse, and researchers attempted to comprehend patients' emotions, physical capacities, and social environment. Patients were viewed as persons as well as active participants. Patients are not always trusted in the uncertain patient discourse. In this discussion, health care providers frequently have a better understanding of what is best for the patient. Patients are invisible to the

radiographer/researcher in the invisible patient discourse. They are just seen as organs, symptoms, or diseases. (Törnroos & Ahonen, 2014).

Non-Indigenous people investigating Indigenous Peoples and environments face complex ethical challenges regarding proper roles, obligations, and approaches. Critical discourse analysis (CDA) is a study methodology that examines language and discourse to reveal colonial power and injustices. This study used a scoping review to look at how non-Indigenous researchers used CDA to analyse speech about People from Australia's Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities. The study comprised a total of eighteen papers. When looking at oppressive power structures, most papers mentioned colonizer colonization, imperialism, white supremacy, and/or structural discrimination.

While some studies included critical theorists' and critical Native theorists' literature, this analysis presented new concerns regarding the methodological foundations of studies. There were many writers with unquestionable power, sociocultural position, and attitude while evaluating Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander People' speak and text, for example. While conducting CDA research in Indigenous contexts, non-Indigenous academics should look into three areas: critical reflexivity, colonial power analysis, and demonstrable anti-racist action. (Julia McCartan et al., 2022).

Discourse and Medical

In transition studies, discourse analysis is gaining traction. This research uses discourse network analysis (DNA) to look explore how discourse coalitions and the storylines they mobilize evolve over time. Using historical data from two daily newspapers, we investigate the coal war. The phase-out period in Germany runs from 2000 to 2020. An anti-coal discourse coalition was discovered. It has been stable and ideationally consistent over time. The main story line was based on climate change. Coal's legitimacy should be revoked. The decision to phase out the policy in 2020 can be considered a win. Coalition. The pro-coal coalition, on the other hand, was more fractured and inconsistent in its reasoning. Despite this, some of its key storylines made it into the final policies. We believe that DNA is an effective tool for understanding politics and other topics. (Markard et al., 2021).

This Clinical Practice Statement (CPS) on Nutrition and Physical Activity from the Obesity Medicine Association (OMA) gives clinicians an overview of nutrition and physical activity principles that apply to the care of patients with excess body fat, particularly those with adverse fat mass and adiposopathic metabolic consequences. The scientific information and clinical advice are based on peer-reviewed evidence and developed from the writers' clinical experiences. Basic clinical information about carbohydrates, proteins, fats (including trans fats, saturated fats, polyunsaturated fats, and monounsaturated fats), general principles of healthy nutrition, nutritional factors associated with improved health outcomes, and food labels are provided in this OMA CPS on Nutrition and Physical Activity. There are also definitions of low-calorie, extremely low-calorie, carbohydrate-restricted, and fat-restricted dietary intakes, as well as the therapeutic implications of isocaloric substitution of refined carbs with saturated fats and vice versa. Carbohydrate-restricted diets, fat-restricted diets, very low-calorie diets, the Mediterranean diet, Therapeutic Lifestyle diet, Dietary

Approaches to Stop Hypertension (DASH), ketogenic (modified Atkins) diet, Ornish diet, Paleo diet, vegetarian or vegan diet (whole food/plant based), intermittent fasting/time restricted feeding, and commercial diet programmes are some of the specific dietary plans discussed. This clinical practice statement also looks at the health advantages of physical activity and offers ideas on the types and levels of dynamic (aerobic) training, resistance (anaerobic) training, leisure time physical activity, and non-exercise activity thermogenesis (NEAT).

Additional information on muscle physiology, exercise prescription, metabolic equivalent tasks (METs), and tracking physical activity improvement is offered. This Clinical Practice Statement on Diet and Physical Exercise from the Obesity Medicine Association gives doctors an overview of nutrition and physical activity. Appropriate nutrition and physical activity may improve the health of people with pre-obesity and/or obesity, particularly those with unfavorable fat mass and adiposopathic metabolic effects. (Alexander et al., 2022).

Methodology

The researcher will use Van Dijk's discourse model to compare the discourse of research journal article recommendations with that of Obesity Association guidelines. The study is a mixed method study since the researcher collected and analyzed data using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Antconc Software will do a word-level comparative analysis of research journals and medical societies. A graphical depiction of vocabulary (word level) will also be provided using an Excell sheet. The researcher collected data from web-documents (research articles, websites) and evaluated it using the Van Dijk discourse model, categorizing the information into Van Dijk's categories of deletion, selection, generalization, and construction. The Vandijk model's results are also expressed in graphical charts. Macrostructure is a sequence of proposition that explicitly represent the global meaning of a text. The macrostructure of a text is obtained through applying to that text the four macro rules of

Deletion deleting information

Selection involves selecting information relevant to the building of macro proposition of the text.

Generalization refers to the process of abstracting from the details of the text

Construction entails substituting local propositions with a macro proposition that denotes a more or less stereotypical sequence of events.

Results and Discussion

Deletion

Deletion are those facts that are recommended by one text but not by the other. For example, medical advisories suggest meditation and treatment about the Obesity, but Research

journals recommend the maintenance of Nutrition, lifestyle parameters, healthy diet, exercise, and prevention from processed foods.

We analyzed these points are deleted by associations as compared with journals

- good choice of food
- physical activities
- Intake Fiber
- Milk
- green leafy vegetables
- proper breakfast
- focus on nutrition's
- prevention of fast food
- less screen timing
- Fresh juice
- Fruits
- Calcium
- Yogurt
- Butter
- Protein

Selection

The basic purpose behind selection is that what one wants they select.

they select on their bias and choice

selection refers to select things according to personal will for business promotion, for sales.

In selection we analyzed which points and facts are selected by associations

- Medicines
- (Bupropion-naltrexone, orlistat (Alli, Xenical)
- Injections
- hydrogels,
- gastric bypass surgery
- gastric sleeve surgery
- intragastric balloon for weight loss
- weight loss devices
- Endoscopic sleeve gastroplasty

Generalization

Generalization is the process of abstracting from the details of the text

(Sameness of things)

We Analyze the Generalization of Both Journals and Associations Bellow

- prevention of fast foods and processed food
- exercise and physical activities
- healthy choices of food

generalization is committed from both the sides, just for to give information and opinion but they don't talk about agenda they possess.

Construction

schema construction

Building of schema through events with the help of language variations.

- Medicines
- (Bupropion-naltrexone, orlistat (Alli, Xenical)
- Injections
- hydrogels,
- surgery
- gastric bypass surgery
- gastric sleeve surgery
- intragastric balloon for weight loss

The words and language choice and selection of associations shows and indicate that associations, advisories want to indicate towards medicines and surgeries by using medical terms and language.

Fig:1 Van Dijk's Model

Tab 1: Key word List with Word and Phrases

Words	Journals	Examples in Journals (word and Phrase level)
Fiber	33	high in fiber, low in calories,
Milk	11	milk consumption was well below the suggested amount,
protein	60	adipose tissue gene/protein expression in humans [142].
junk food	3	A minimum percentage of subjects have this junk food every day (less than the 4.5% in every group).
Medicines	87	Internal Medicine and Endocrinology and Metabolism, obesity medicine provider,
Surgery	49	bariatric surgery.
physical activities	4	intensity physical activities physical activities are associated with high BAT density in humans
Fat	334	saturated fat, and refined carbohydrates. body fat may enhance body fat diagnosis.
Obesity	791	American Board of Obesity Medicine obesity specialists engaged in the clinical management of obesity among patients of South Asian descent.
Weight	427	weight loss medications weight related complications
Exercise	361	Exercise Medicine Exercise Questionnaire and total leisure activity
Metabolism	44	Adipose tissue metabolism is still controversial tissue and metabolism.
Ketogenic	31	low-carbohydrate ketogenic diet ketogenic diet is sometimes associated with individual,
polyunsaturated	23	Polyunsaturated fats hydrogenating polyunsaturated fats (vegetable oils) into more saturated fats,
Sweetened	9	sweetened beverages,
Fitness	12	physical fitness and ability for all activities fitness for adults

To answer my first question, I looked into the parallels and differences in medical research and association directory suggestions. On a textual level, researchers are more detailed and precise, speaking or using language just for the purpose of conveying knowledge, fully ignoring social context, class, or set up. While associations give a list of possible therapies for obesity, the advice are not presented in the form of different levels of obesity.

Disease causes are primarily focused in research journals. In answer of second question both research journals and recommendations employ different discourse to establish their point of view, according to the answer to the second question. Medical groups utilize medical and technical jargon to discuss obesity, while research journals employ a variety of criteria and vocabulary to discuss the disorder. Both sides are attempting to promote their agendas. To answer third question, instead than demonstrating the consequences of obesity, associations are expected to pinpoint the causes. To establish whether or not a dietary intake is good for the human body, emphasize the sugary and carbohydrate content of various foods. Medical recommendations, promote meditation and treatment for obesity, whereas research publications advise maintaining nutrition, lifestyle parameters, a healthy diet, exercise, and avoiding processed foods. From this perspective we conclude that associations deleted natural treatment of obesity by deleted those factors.

The basic purpose behind selection is that what one wants they select, they select on their bias and choice. selection refers to select things according to personal will for business promotion. Associations selected and prefer surgeries and medicines it is clear that they are promoting their business and agenda. The process of generalization is abstracting from the details of the text, generalization is committed from both the sides, just for to give information and opinion but they don't talk about agenda they possess.

The words and language choice and selection of associations shows and indicate that associations, advisories want to indicate towards medicines and surgeries by using medical terms and language. Both sides have completely different language variations and constructions. Language descriptions and terminology of research and medical recommendations show their goals by exposing syntactic variances. (Julia McCartan et al., 2022). Significant differences in the recommended presentations were identified in the comparison summary. The study articles offer suggestions and, as a result, therapeutic recommendations based on the degree of the obesity. Instead of offering advice in the form of different levels of obesity, the organizations provide a list of viable cures.

Obesity causes must be investigated in accordance with the conclusions of medical research papers. Instead of showing the effects of obesity, associations are expected to specifically identify the causes of obesity. Give prominence to the sugary and carbohydrate content of various foods to determine whether or not the dietary intake is good for the human body.

(Yolie J.E. Michielsen & Horst, 2022). The comparative summary revealed significant disparities in the recommended presentations. According to the severity of the obesity, the study articles provide suggestions and, as a result, advise treatment. The organizations, on the other hand, give a list of possible remedies rather than advice in the form of different levels of obesity. On a textual level, researchers are more detailed and precise, speaking or using language just for the purpose of conveying knowledge, fully ignoring social context, class, or set up. (Törnroos & Ahonen, 2014). While organizations give a list of potential therapies for obesity, they do not present advice in the form of different levels of obesity. The cause and recommendation parts of medical research publications and medical associations have a lot of differences. To begin with, the medical associations' reasons of obesity are fairly broad. Second, neither the diet that causes obesity nor the diet that helps people lose weight is highlighted. Similarly, the associations' Obesity treatment advice are generalized, and the diet habits that must be followed throughout Obesity are advised. Obesity patients are not appropriately guided about the specific causes that contribute to Obesity development and therapy by generalist Obesity causes and recommendations.

If we talk about the whole study, associations focus more on medicines, surgeries, injections, and weight reduction equipment, whereas research studies only focus on healthy dietary choices, carbohydrate avoidance, and fiber and calcium protein intake. (Alexander et al., 2022). There are however some aspects that are consistent across correlations and research studies, such as reduced screen time, physical activity, and the avoidance of junk foods. Finally, we can claim that we should follow the research studies because they are the safest and simplest way to lose weight. (Vertinsky, 1988). To summaries, advisories and associations are sprinkling dust in the eyes of the public in order to promote their businesses and wealth, and this scheme is being carried out in large part because they want to control the world according to their own version of events, and this process of recommending unbalanced meditations may lead to further diseases. Apart from that, we may deduce that there is a significant distinction between suggestions and recommendations, which is revealed through discursive analysis of both advisories and journals.

CONCLUSION

It's all about comprehending language in context, which includes background information, the goals that drive the language, and the behaviours that arise from specific lexical choices. The study of text production, discursive practice, and social practice is referred to as discourse. (Burr, 2003, p. 68). Who is speaking to whom, what is being said, why is it being said, how is it being spoken, and where is it being said? (Shilling, 2003). This is a qualitative and descriptive study of medical text analysis; in this paper, I looked at the similarities and differences in medical research and association directory recommendations. On a textual level, researchers are more detailed and precise, speaking or using language just for the purpose of conveying knowledge, fully ignoring social context, class, or set up. While associations give a list of possible therapies for obesity, the advice are not presented in the form of different levels of obesity. . (Yolie J.E. Michielsen & Horst, 2022). It has been concluded that advisories and associations are sprinkling dust in the eyes of the public in order to promote their business and wealth, and that this conspiracy is being carried out in large part because they want to control the world according to their own version of events, and that this process of recommending irregular meditations can lead to more diseases. (Alexander et al., 2022). From this perspective, we may conclude that all brands and medical associations are supporting Karl Marx's theory of materialism, with all of its evidences plainly stated in the associations' recommendations. They simply want to promote their business.

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